

RADIATION HARVESTING OF BIOACTIVE PEPTIDES FROM EGG PROTEINS AND THEIR INTEGRATION IN ADVANCED FUNCTIONAL PRODUCTS

INNOVATION ACTION OF HORIZON EUROPE EURATOM RESEARCH AND TRAINING PROGRAMME GA N° 101061694

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Database on structure-process and structure-activity relationship

DELIVERABLE: D2.8

Document identifier:	RADOV-Del-D2.8
Due date of deliverable:	End of month 24 (August 2024)
Report release date:	03/10/2025
Justification for delay:	WP2 duration was extended to collect more data. Moreover, data presented in this report needed to be aligned with the bioactivity results (D2.5).
Work package:	WP2 [Development of laboratory scale production of irradiated egg products and peptides]
Lead beneficiary:	KTH
Document status:	Final

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Training programme under Grant Agreement No 101061694.

RADOV began in September 2022 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	Mats Jonsson	KTH	28/02/2025
Edited by	Åsa Emmer	KTH	28/02/2025
Reviewed by	Steering Committee	All Partners	10/10/2025
Approved by	Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko	INCT	10/10/2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	3
2. Results	3
2.1 Protein structure	3
2.2 Irradiation conditions	6
2.3 Conversion yields	6
2.4 Characterization of irradiated products.	8
2.5 Bioactivity	11
3. Database	13
4. Structure-process and structure-activity relationships	13
5. References	14
6. Database on different irradiated hen egg products	14

Executive summary

To conclude the work performed in WP2, a deliverable presenting a database and structure-process and structure-activity relationships based on the data in the database was planned. In this report, qualitative relationships are presented for the limited cases where product structure and bioactivity are known to some extent. The systems discussed in terms of these relationship are solid-state irradiated lysozyme and ovalbumin as well as lysozyme irradiated in aqueous solution under reducing conditions (1 M 2-propanol purged with N₂ prior to irradiation).

1. Introduction

To conclude the work performed in WP2, a deliverable presenting a database and structure-process and structure-activity relationships based on the data in the database was planned. The initial plan was based on the production and characterization of peptides isolated from proteins irradiated under various conditions. The assumption was that peptides formed upon radiation-induced scission of egg proteins would display bioactivity beyond the egg proteins themselves. However, the work within WP2 has shown that irradiation of egg proteins does not lead to the formation of significant fractions of peptides. In some cases, the formation of fragments can be observed but never to the extent required to be able to isolate a given fraction. For this reason, the focus of this deliverable has been shifted from well-defined peptides to less defined products. Even though it was not possible to produce peptide fractions, egg proteins exposed to ionizing radiation under certain conditions display increased bioactivity.

In this report, the structure of proteins and products formed upon irradiation of proteins will be related to irradiation conditions and bioactivity.

2. Results

2.1 Protein structure

The amino acid composition of the three hen egg proteins used in this project are listed in tables 1-3.

Lysozyme is a small-sized, globular protein consisting of 129 amino acids in total and with a molecular weight of around 14 kDa. It consists of 8 cysteine residues, forming four disulfide bridges, which gives the protein its high conformational

stability.

Table 1. Amino acid composition of lysozyme, which consists of 129 amino acids in total.

Amino acid	Number	Percentage
Alanine (A)	12	9.3 %
Arginine (R)	11	8.5 %
Asparagine (N)	14	10.9 %
Aspartic acid (D)	7	5.4%
Cysteine (C)	8	6.2 %
Glutamic acid (E)	2	1.6 %
Glutamine (Q)	3	2.3 %
Glycine (G)	12	9.3 %
Histidine (H)	1	0.8 %
Isoleucine (I)	6	4.7 %
Leucine (L)	8	6.2 %
Lysine (K)	6	4.7 %
Methionine (M)	2	1.6 %
Phenylalanine (F)	3	2.3 %
Proline (P)	2	1.6 %
Serine (S)	10	7.8 %
Threonine (T)	7	5.4 %
Tryptophan (W)	6	4.7 %
Tyrosine (Y)	3	2.3 %
Valine (V)	6	4.7 %

Ovalbumin is an average-sized globular protein consisting of 386 amino acids in total and with a molecular weight of around 43 kDa. Out of the six cysteine moieties, two make up a disulfide bridge, while the remaining four provide free thiol groups. The amino acid profile can be considered balanced, and it is a quite stable protein.

Table 2. Amino acid composition of ovalbumin, which consists of 386 amino acids in total.

Amino acid	Number	Percentage
Alanine (A)	35	9.1 %
Arginine (R)	15	3.9 %
Asparagine (N)	17	4.4 %
Aspartic acid (D)	14	3.6 %
Cysteine (C)	6	1.6 %
Glutamic acid (E)	33	8.5 %
Glutamine (Q)	15	3.9 %
Glycine (G)	19	4.9 %
Histidine (H)	7	1.8 %
Isoleucine (I)	25	6.5 %
Leucine (L)	32	8.3 %
Lysine (K)	20	5.2 %

Methionine (M)	17	4.4 %
Phenylalanine (F)	20	5.2 %
Proline (P)	14	3.6 %
Serine (S)	38	9.8 %
Threonine (T)	15	3.9 %
Tryptophan (W)	3	0.8 %
Tyrosine (Y)	10	2.6 %
Valine (V)	31	8.0 %

Ovotransferrin is a relatively large, unstable, globular protein consisting of 686 amino acids and with a molecular weight of around 76 kDa. There are 30 cysteines, all participating in creating 15 disulfide bonds.

Table 3. Amino acid composition of ovotransferrin, which consists of 686 amino acids in total.

Amino acid	Number	Percentage
Alanine (A)	54	7.9 %
Arginine (R)	30	4.4 %
Asparagine (N)	30	4.4 %
Aspartic acid (D)	46	6.7 %
Cysteine (C)	30	4.4 %
Glutamic acid (E)	45	6.6 %
Glutamine (Q)	23	3.4 %
Glycine (G)	52	7.6 %
Histidine (H)	12	1.7 %
Isoleucine (I)	26	3.8 %
Leucine (L)	49	7.1 %
Lysine (K)	59	8.6 %
Methionine (M)	11	1.6 %
Phenylalanine (F)	26	3.8 %
Proline (P)	28	4.1 %
Serine (S)	48	7.0 %
Threonine (T)	37	5.4 %
Tryptophan (W)	10	1.5 %
Tyrosine (Y)	21	3.1 %
Valine (V)	49	7.1 %

When we look at the amino acid composition of the three proteins, we notice that lysozyme contains the greatest percentage of amino acids with antioxidative capacity (28.8 %), followed by ovotransferrin (25.3 %), and ovalbumin (20.3 %) [1]. The fractions of amino acids with antioxidative capacity for the three proteins are listed in table 4.

Table 4. Fractions of amino acids with antioxidant properties in lysozyme, ovalbumin and ovotransferrin

Amino acid	Lysozyme	Ovalbumin	Ovotransferrin
Arginine (R)	8.5%	3.9%	4.4%
Cysteine (C)	6.2%	1.6%	4.4%
Histidine (H)	0.8%	1.8%	1.7%
Lysine (K)	4.7%	5.2%	8.6%
Methionine (M)	1.6%	4.4%	1.6%
Tryptophan (W)	4.7%	0.8%	1.5%
Tyrosine (Y)	2.3%	2.6%	3.1%

2.2 Irradiation conditions

The irradiation conditions are given in the database (attached). The expected impact of changing the conditions is discussed in D2.1. Table 5 lists the different parameters that have been evaluated, resulting in over 250 unique conditions.

Table 5. List of parameters in irradiation of proteins and egg products.

Parameter	
Physical state	Solid state /Aqueous solution
Atmosphere	Air/N ₂ O/N ₂
Radiation	High energy electrons/ γ -radiation
Temperature	Room temperature/Dry ice
Dose	1 and 10 kGy (and up to 500 kGy)
Co-Solute	None/Phosphate buffer/TRIS/2-propanol
Protein concentration	0.05 – 10 mg/ml

2.3 Conversion yields

The first step in being able to quantify process efficiency is to determine the conversion yields. In radiation chemistry, so-called radiation chemical yields or G-values are used. Radiation chemical yields are defined as amount of substance consumed or produced per unit of radiation energy absorbed. The SI-unit is mol/J but it is quite common to find the unit number of molecules/100 eV in the literature. In the following text we focus on the G-values for consumption of protein based on MALDI TOF analysis.

The consumption of lysozyme in aqueous solutions at 1 mg/ml under air, N₂ or N₂O, and in the absence or presence of phosphate buffer corresponds to radiation chemical yields for protein consumption in the order of 5-6 x 10⁻⁸ mol/J.

In the systems containing 2-propanol, the solutions were purged with N₂ prior to irradiation in order to remove dissolved oxygen. The main radiolysis products formed under these conditions are the hydrated electron (e⁻aq) and the hydroxyl radical. The latter (and the hydrogen atom) reacts with 2-propanol and the major product of this reaction is the strongly reducing 2-hydroxy-2-propyl radical. Hence, the system becomes reducing. It has been shown that protein consumption is mainly (but not only) driven by the hydrated electron. Irradiations performed using 1 mg/ml lysozyme and either 2-propanol or t-butanol (a hydroxyl radical scavenger that does not produce a reducing radical) show that the 2-hydroxy-2-propyl radical contributes to some extent to the consumption of lysozyme. The estimated radiation chemical yield for protein consumption is 5.5 x 10⁻⁸ mol/J under these conditions. The G-value for the hydrated electron is 2.8 x 10⁻⁷ mol/J. Given the fact that the hydrated electron has been reported to have a very high rate constant for the reaction with lysozyme, the efficiency of this reaction would appear to be quite low. A possible rationale for this is that the molar concentration of protein molecules is quite low from the beginning.

Based on initial protein conversion, the radiation chemical yield for protein alteration in the solid state is 6.3 x 10⁻⁷, 6.2 x 10⁻⁷ and 6.8 x 10⁻⁷ mol/J for lysozyme, ovalbumin and ovotransferrin, respectively. Interestingly, the radiation chemical yields are independent of protein structure. Due to the large differences in molecular weight, the doses required for full protein conversion differ significantly between the proteins. For proteins with higher molecular weight (ovotransferrin and ovalbumin), fewer alterations per unit mass are required to reach full conversion of the starting material.

The G-values for protein consumption/conversion are summarized in table 6

Table 6. Radiation chemical yields for protein alteration under different irradiation conditions.

Protein	Irradiation conditions	G-value (mol/J)
Lysozyme	Aqueous solution, N ₂ /N ₂ O/Air, with and without PBS*	5-6 x 10 ⁻⁸
Lysozyme	Aqueous solution, 2-propanol, N ₂	5.5 x 10 ⁻⁸
Lysozyme	Solid-state	6.3 x 10 ⁻⁷
Ovalbumin	Solid-state	6.2 x 10 ⁻⁷
Ovotransferrin	Solid-state	6.8 x 10 ⁻⁷

*Note that these are six different conditions.

2.4 Characterization of irradiated products

Gamma- and electron beam irradiation of aqueous protein solutions saturated with air or purged with N₂O (or N₂) were often found to produce soluble or insoluble aggregates.

Based on both MALDI-TOF and SDS-page, irradiations of the proteins in solution under reducing conditions induces protein fragmentation. This is particularly obvious for lysozyme. From experiments where the reducing conditions were obtained in different ways it was concluded that protein fragmentation can mainly be attributed to reactions with the hydrated electron with a minor contribution from the 2-hydroxy-2-propyl radical. However, it should be stressed that fragmentation to a detectable size fraction only accounts for a minor part of the overall protein consumption.

Interestingly, the increase in the amount of detectable fraction of smaller fragments formed upon irradiation of lysozyme in aqueous solution under reducing conditions does not parallel the consumption of lysozyme. This could imply that the detectable fraction represents a reaction intermediate rather than a final product. In other words, it is possible that the observable fragments undergo further fragmentation upon extended irradiation. This is well in line with the arguments given above concerning the low radiation chemical yield for protein conversion. If this is the case, fragments of the desired size need to be harvested at an early stage. Given the fact that the fragments formed will be present in a high molar concentration compared to the protein, it is probable that the hydrated electrons will primarily react with the fragments in competition with the protein.

For the solid-state irradiated proteins, fragmentation is also observed.

As MALDI TOF, SDS-page and liquid chromatography did not reveal any sizeable product fractions that could be isolated for further analysis and use in the applications developed in WP3, alternative methods have been used to identify alterations induced by ionizing radiation. The techniques used are FTIR, Raman spectroscopy, MALDI-TOF MS/MS and NMR. The results from these studies are summarized below:

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

ATR-FTIR analysis was performed on non-irradiated proteins dissolved in ultra pure water at concentrations ranging from 1 mg/mL to 5 mg/mL. The experimental setup was configured with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and 64 scans, and with the x-axis range set between 4000 and 500 cm⁻¹. The samples exhibited low absorbance, with no significant peaks observed, likely due to insufficient concentration. Increasing concentration was not feasible, as it led to undissolved solids remaining in the solution. Attempts to dissolve the sample in acetonitrile (1 mg/mL) were

unsuccessful. Similarly, dissolving non-irradiated lysozyme (1 mg/mL) in heavy water yielded results comparable to the water-dissolved samples, showing low absorbance and no significant peaks.

Pellets of non-irradiated lysozyme, ovotransferrin, and ovalbumin mixed with potassium bromide (KBr) were also analyzed using transmission FTIR. Additionally, dry irradiated lysozyme samples at doses of 50 kGy and 500 kGy were examined. Non-irradiated samples dried in a desiccator for one week and in an oven at 50°C for three hours were also analyzed. All samples exhibited similar results, displaying broad and intense peaks corresponding to protein amide bands, which likely represents the protein backbone. No distinct functionalities were identified in these spectra.

Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy was attempted on both solid and liquid (1 mg/mL) non-irradiated lysozyme samples. The solid sample exhibited a single intense peak dominating the entire spectrum, likely due to excessive fluorescence. The liquid sample also showed fluorescence, but aside from that, only water peaks were observed. The low concentration may have further hindered the Raman analysis.

MALDI-TOF MS/MS

MS/MS analysis was attempted on dry irradiated lysozyme (300 kGy), ovotransferrin (200 kGy), ovalbumin (200 kGy), and isopropanol-irradiated lysozyme (5 kGy) samples, all at a concentration of 3 mg/mL. However, the parent ion was not detectable, most likely due to the low concentration, preventing fragmentation analysis. A further attempt to analyze isopropanol-irradiated lysozyme (5 kGy) at a concentration of 10 mg/mL was also unsuccessful, as the sample remained undetectable.

NMR

All measurements were conducted at 500 MHz ¹H resonance frequency on a Bruker 500 Avance HD spectrometer, equipped with a 5 mm DIFF30 probe capable of generating a unidirectional (z-axis) gradient with a maximum value of 1800 G/cm. The actual experiments relied on the stimulated echo pulse sequence with the diffusion time Δ set to 100 ms and with the strength g of the $\delta = 1$ ms long gradient pulse stepped from 5 G/cm to either 250 G/cm (for lysozyme samples) or to 350 G/cm (for ovalbumin samples).

The self-diffusion coefficients were extracted by fitting the variation of the spectral integral intensity of the ¹H protein signal with increasing gradient strength to the customary Stejskal-Tanner expression

$$\ln\left(\frac{S(g)}{S(g)}\right) \sim -(\gamma g \delta)^2 \left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{3}\right) D$$

where γ is the magnetogyric ratio of ^1H . Integrated intensities in the aromatic (6-9.5 ppm) and aliphatic (0-3 ppm) spectral regions (water signal set to 4.7 ppm) provided, within experimental error, the same diffusion behaviour in all investigated samples.

All solid-state irradiated lysozyme samples have exhibited, within error, the same self-diffusion coefficient ($0.98 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ for the 50 kGy sample and $0.96 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ for the 500 kGy sample) as the non-irradiated sample ($0.99 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$). This value is close to literature values ([https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-4838\(97\)00224-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-4838(97)00224-0)) and is in line with the known hydrodynamic radius of approx. 2 nm. Hence, solid-state irradiation does not lead to a detectable break-up of lysozyme. On the other hand, the ^1H NMR spectrum in the 500 kGy sample shows significant changes relative to the spectrum of the non-irradiated sample, particularly in the aliphatic region. This points to changes in a large fraction of selected amino acids/moieties. To assign the affected moieties, high-field and high-resolution ^1H COSY and HSQC experiments would be required. The 50 kGy sample witnessed the same spectral changes but to much lesser (by estimate, an order of magnitude less) extent.

The lysozyme irradiated in aqueous solution under reducing conditions to 100 kGy have exhibited a clear two-component (or rather, a clearly more-than-a-single-component) diffusional decay. A two-component fit provided relative intensities of approx. 50% of each component and with self-diffusion coefficients $D_{\text{fast}} = 4.1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and $D_{\text{slow}} = 1.1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. Having fitted with a single-component function, one obtains a measure of the average self-diffusion coefficient $\langle D \rangle = 1.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. Note that two-exponential fits (of two-component decays) are inherently less accurate than single-exponential fits (of one-component decays). Hence, the data are consistent with having roughly half of the lysozyme molecules intact (that is, not broken up, though chemically modified, see below), while the other half broken up to small (on average, approx. 0.5 nm hydrodynamic radius) fragments. (In this context, ^1H NMR intensity is proportional to the molar concentration of select moieties.) The 10 kGy lysozyme sample (aqueous solution, reducing conditions) showed no clear-cut two-component diffusional decay, yet $\langle D \rangle$ obtained by a one-component fit increased to $1.12 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ from the non-irradiated value ($0.99 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$). Hence, fragmentation is present already at 10 kGy.

The aliphatic region of the ^1H NMR spectra of the lysozyme samples irradiated in aqueous solution under reducing conditions is very different from the non-irradiated case. In particular, the spectrum of the 100 kGy sample shows no resemblance to the non-irradiated sample (to the extent of no recognizable lysozyme spectrum left)

indicating significant changes to most of the constituting amino acids. Note also that solid-state irradiation (at 500 kGy) and irradiation in aqueous solution under reducing conditions (at either 10 or 100 kGy) causes quite different changes to the involved moieties as witnessed by the very different aliphatic spectral regions.

The non-irradiated ovalbumin sample exhibited $D = 6.2 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ which is consistent with its known hydrodynamic radius of approx. 2.7 nm. The 500 kGy solid-state irradiated ovalbumin sample have exhibited a more-than-a-single-component diffusional decay. A two-component fit provided relative intensities of approx. 50% of each component and with self-diffusion coefficients $D_{\text{fast}} = 1.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and $D_{\text{slow}} = 5.5 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. Again, this yields that half of ovalbumin is roughly intact, while the other half was turned into smaller (on average, approx. 0.9 nm hydrodynamic radius) fragments.

The aliphatic regions of the ^1H NMR spectra of non-irradiated and 500 kGy solid-state irradiated ovalbumin samples are quite different from each other, yet the peaks that grow in the 500 kGy case are recognizable in the non-irradiated spectrum. Hence, significant changes to a large fraction of the constituting amino acids occur, yet on a manner that is perhaps different from the lysozyme case. One slightly peculiar observation – the aromatic ^1H spectral fraction of ovalbumin is much smaller than that of lysozyme, yet irradiation seems to affect much more the aromatic ^1H spectral region in ovalbumin. Additional experiments (see above) would be needed to be able to say more.

2.5 Bioactivity

The full set of data on bioactivity is presented in D2.5. At the time of finalizing deliverable D2.8, the most pronounced bioactivity observed is antioxidant activity. It should be pointed out that even if the proteins contain fairly high fractions of amino acids with antioxidant properties, the antioxidant activity of the unirradiated proteins is very low. Antioxidant activity as function of absorbed dose is graphically illustrated in the figures below.

Figure 1. Antioxidant activity (FRAP) for solid-state irradiated proteins as a function of dose (protein concentration in FRAP assay 20 mg/ml)

Figure 2. Antioxidant activity (FRAP) for lysozyme irradiated in aqueous solution under reducing conditions at 1 and 5 mg/ml (protein concentration in FRAP assay 20 mg/ml)

For lysozyme irradiated in aqueous solution under air, N₂ or N₂O, the antioxidant activity according to FRAP is more than twice as high as for lysozyme irradiated in aqueous solution under reducing conditions. Interestingly, the antioxidant activity does not change with absorbed dose (between 10 and 50 kGy) under these conditions and it appears to be independent of atmosphere. For ovotransferrin, the antioxidant activity (FRAP) is comparable to lysozyme under N₂O-atmosphere but considerably lower under air and N₂. No data on dose dependence are available.

3. Database

A database including all the irradiation conditions used in the project and observations based on different types of product characterization is included in Section 6. As D2.5 will be delivered later than D2.8, a complete database including also bioactivity data cannot be presented at this point. The database will be completed when D2.5 has been submitted. The database will continue to be developed during the remaining project period as new data become available.

4. Structure-process and structure-activity relationships

The structure-process and structure-activity relationships can be expressed in different ways depending on the level of structural information available. As shown above, the structural information about the products formed upon irradiation is very limited (since no sizeable well-defined fractions of peptides are formed under the irradiation conditions tested).

We can explore the correlation between protein structure and susceptibility to radiation-induced alterations, the correlation between processing conditions and product structure and the correlation between product structure and antioxidant properties. Admittedly, these relationships cannot be quantitative at this point.

Correlation between protein structure and susceptibility to radiation-induced alterations

The only irradiation condition where conversion data is available is solid-state irradiation using electron beam. Lysozyme, ovalbumin and ovotransferrin were irradiated under these conditions. The resulting conversion G-values (based on consumption of the starting material) are all in the range $6.2-6.8 \times 10^{-7}$ mol/J. In other words, consumption of the protein is independent of the structure (at least when comparing these three proteins).

Correlation between processing conditions and product structure

The preliminary NMR results presented above provide some insights regarding the product structure. At this point the data set is quite limited but we can still draw some interesting conclusions.

For lysozyme we can see that the processing conditions have a strong impact on the product structure. For lysozyme irradiated in the solid-state, no change in size is

observed but there are changes in functionality. The change in functionality is mainly related to the aliphatic functionality and it is clear that the change in functionality is dose dependent. For lysozyme irradiated in aqueous solution under reducing conditions there is a considerable reduction in size and significant changes in functionality.

Solid-state irradiation of lysozyme and ovalbumin reveal some structure-dependent differences. For ovalbumin, it is clear that radiation induces scission. Given the fact that ovalbumin is a much larger molecule than lysozyme, it is not surprising that scission can be observed for ovalbumin but not for lysozyme at a given dose. The chemical modification of ovalbumin appears different from that of lysozyme. This could possibly be connected to the difference in protein structure.

Correlation between product structure and antioxidant properties

From the available data on antioxidant properties and on structural changes upon irradiation, we can conclude that more extensive changes in functionality (as seen when increasing the dose in solid-state irradiation) increases antioxidant activity. The irradiation in aqueous solution under reducing conditions induce more significant fragmentation as well as changes in functionality than in the case of solid-state irradiation. The product from the irradiation in aqueous solution under reducing conditions also displays a significantly higher antioxidant activity. However, based on the available information we cannot say if the enhanced antioxidant activity should be attributed to scission or to changes in chemical functionality (or both).

Proteins irradiated in aqueous solution under air, N₂ or N₂O display the highest antioxidant activity. Under these conditions, fragmentation has not been observed but aggregation is often reported. Based on what is currently known, it is not possible to assign a structural feature to the superior antioxidant activity.

5. References

[1] Xu N, Chen G, Liu H. Antioxidative Categorization of Twenty Amino Acids Based on Experimental Evaluation. *Molecules*. 2017;22(12):2066. Published 2017 Nov 27.

doi:10.3390/molecules22122066

[Antioxidative Categorization of Twenty Amino Acids Based on Experimental Evaluation - PMC](#)

6. Database for different irradiated hen egg products

Sample: **Lysozyme**

IRRADIATION									pH			DATE			STORAGE	ANALYSIS									
Sample ID	Institute	Place of delivery	Atmosphere	Solution composition	Concentration	Source	Dose	Temperature	Before irradiation	After irradiation	After shipment/ before analysis	of irradiation	of receipt	of analysis	Type of storage	Visual observations	Analysis			Without DTT			With DTT		
																	Analysis method	Analysis performed at	Consumption of native protein	Fragments	Aggregates	Consumption of native protein	Fragments	Aggregates	
INCT-1GLD-11L-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	1 kGy	RT				24.10.2022			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	No	No			Marginally	Few	
INCT-1GLD-10L-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	10 kGy	RT				24.10.2022			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	No	No			Marginally	Few	
INCT-1GLD-51L-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	5 kGy	RT				24.10.2022													
INCT-1GLD-101L-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	10 kGy	RT				24.10.2022													
INCT-1GLD-251L-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	25 kGy	RT				24.10.2022													
INCT-1LS-1EL-RN/ INCT-1LS-1EL-RNPO	INCT	KTH	N2O	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	
INCT-1LS-1EL-RA/ INCT-1LS-1EL-RAPO	INCT	KTH	Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	
INCT-1LS-1EL-RI/ INCT-1LS-1EL-RIPO	INCT	KTH	N2	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	
INCT-1LS-1EL-RNP/ INCT-1LS-1EL-RNPOP	INCT	KTH	N2O	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C	Precipitation	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	
INCT-1LS-1EL-RAP/ INCT-1LS-1EL-RAPOP	INCT	KTH	Air	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C	Precipitation	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	
INCT-1LS-1EL-RIP/ INCT-1LS-1EL-RIPOP	INCT	KTH	N2	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C	Precipitation	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	
INCT-1LS-10EL-RN/ INCT-1LS-10EL-RNPO	INCT	KTH	N2O	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	
INCT-1LS-10EL-RA/ INCT-1LS-10EL-RAPO	INCT	KTH	Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	
INCT-1LS-10EL-RI/ INCT-1LS-10EL-RIPO	INCT	KTH	N2	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few				Few, but very low intensity	

INCT-1LS-10EL-RNP/ INCT-1LS-10EL-RNPO	INCT	KTH	N2O	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C	Precipitation	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few			Few, but very low intensity
INCT-1LS-10EL-RAP/ INCT-1LS-10EL-RAPO	INCT	KTH	Air	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C	Precipitation	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few			Few, but very low intensity
INCT-1LS-10EL-RIP/ INCT-1LS-10EL-RIPO	INCT	KTH	N2	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18° C	Precipitation	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Few			Few, but very low intensity
INCT-2LS-1EL-RN/ INCT-2LS-1EL-RNPO	INCT	EPS	N2O	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-1EL-RA/ INCT-2LS-1EL-RAPO	INCT	EPS	Air	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-1EL-RI/ INCT-2LS-1EL-RIPO	INCT	EPS	N2	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-1EL-RNP/ INCT-2LS-1EL-RNPO	INCT	EPS	N2O	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-1EL-RAP/ INCT-2LS-1EL-RAPO	INCT	EPS	Air	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-1EL-RIP/ INCT-2LS-1EL-RIPO	INCT	EPS	N2	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-10EL-RN/ INCT-2LS-10EL-RNPO	INCT	EPS	N2O	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-10EL-RA/ INCT-2LS-10EL-RAPO	INCT	EPS	Air	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-10EL-RI/ INCT-2LS-10EL-RIPO	INCT	EPS	N2	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-10EL-RNP/ INCT-2LS-10EL-RNPO	INCT	EPS	N2O	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-10EL-RAP/ INCT-2LS-10EL-RAPO	INCT	EPS	Air	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-10EL-RIP/ INCT-2LS-10EL-RIPO	INCT	EPS	N2	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-1EL-RN	INCT	IST-ID	N2O	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-1EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											
INCT-2LS-1EL-RI	INCT	IST-ID	N2	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023											

INCT-0.1GLD-50EL-RA	INCT	-	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT				23.03.2023			RT, desiccator		gel electrophoresis	INCT		No				
INCT-0.1GLD-100EL-RA	INCT	-	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT				23.03.2023			RT, desiccator		gel electrophoresis	INCT		No				
INCT-0.1GLD-200EL-RA	INCT	-	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT				23.03.2023			RT, desiccator		gel electrophoresis	INCT		No				
INCT-0.1GLD-300EL-RA	INCT	-	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT				23.03.2023			RT, desiccator		gel electrophoresis	INCT		No				
INCT-LD-50EL-RA	INCT	EPS	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-LD-100EL-RA	INCT	EPS	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-LD-200EL-RA	INCT	EPS	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-LD-300EL-RA	INCT	EPS	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-LD-50EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT		4,31	17.05.2023	01-06-23	08-06-23		-	Solubility test DLS	UNIPA	No	No	Yes				
INCT-LD-100EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT		4,11	17.05.2023	01-06-23	08-06-23		-	Solubility test DLS	UNIPA	No	No	Yes				
INCT-LD-200EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT		3,84	17.05.2023	01-06-23	08-06-23		-	Solubility test DLS	UNIPA	No	No	Yes				
INCT-LD-300EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT		3,7	17.05.2023	01-06-23	08-06-23		-	Solubility test DLS	UNIPA	No	No	No				
INCT-1LS-20EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	KTH	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	20 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Marginally	No				
INCT-1LS-40EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	KTH	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	40 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Marginally	No				
INCT-1LS-60EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	KTH	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	60 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				
INCT-1LS-80EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	KTH	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	80 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				
INCT-1LS-100EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	KTH	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023			Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				No
INCT-1LS-20EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	IST-ID	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	20 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023												
INCT-1LS-40EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	IST-ID	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	40 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023												
INCT-1LS-60EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	IST-ID	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	60 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023												
INCT-1LS-80EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	IST-ID	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	80 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023												
INCT-1LS-100EL-FI-TRIS	INCT	IST-ID	N2	TRIS	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	Frozen (dry ice)				31.05.2023												
		KTH	Air	H2O	1.5 mg/ml	γ-source	1.1 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						Few
		KTH	Air	H2O	5 mg/ml	γ-source	1.1 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes					Few
		KTH	Air	H2O	1.5 mg/ml	γ-source	11 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes					Few
		KTH	Air	H2O	5 mg/ml	γ-source	11 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes					Few
		KTH	Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	γ-source	26 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes					
		KTH	Air	H2O	10 mg/ml	γ-source	26 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes					
		KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	γ-source	26 kGy	RT							RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	No				Marginally	
		KTH	Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	γ-source	43 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C	Precipitation	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes					
		KTH	Air	H2O	10 mg/ml	γ-source	43 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes					
		KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	γ-source	43 kGy	RT							RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	No					
		KTH	Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	γ-source	60.5 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes					

																	SDS-PAGE	KTH	Still a strong band at 14 kDa	Blue smear below 10 kDa appear	Faint band around 35 kDa	Still a strong band at 14 kDa	Blue smear below 10 kDa, more like a band	No
	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	500 kGy	RT			11.10.2023						MALDI-TOF	KTH		m/z 562, 647, 1715, 1886, 2001 (S/N =>10) Very low intensity	Not detected	-	m/z 886, 929, 973 (S/N =>10) Very low intensity	Not detected
																	HPLC-UV	KTH	Yes	A couple new peaks, however, very low intensity		Yes	A few new peaks, however, very low intensity	
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH	Still a strong band at 14 kDa, perhaps a bit lighter	Blue smear below 10 kDa appear	Faint band around 35 kDa	Still a strong band at 14 kDa, perhaps a bit lighter	Blue smear below 10 kDa, more like a band	No
	KTH		N2	1 M t-BuOH	1 mg/ml	γ-source	1.1 kGy	RT			12.12.2022	-	13.12.2023	Freezer, -18° C			MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		N2	1 M t-BuOH	1 mg/ml	γ-source	2.2 kGy	RT			12.12.2023	-	13.12.2023	Freezer, -18° C			MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		N2	1 M t-BuOH	1 mg/ml	γ-source	3.6 kGy	RT			12.12.2023	-	13.12.2023	Freezer, -18° C			MALDI-TOF	KTH						
INCT-LD-50EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT				02-29-24	03-12-24	RT	-		UNIPA	No	No	Yes				
INCT-LD-100EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT				02-29-24	03-12-24	RT	-		UNIPA	No	No	Yes				
INCT-LD-200EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT				02-29-24	03-12-24	RT	-	DLS	UNIPA	No	No	Yes				
INCT-LD-300EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT				02-29-24	03-12-24	RT	-	DLS	UNIPA	No	No	No				
INCT-1LS-1EL-R11M	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT	3,69	3,27							MALDI-TOF	KTH		m/z 492, 648, 650*, 751, 766, 1009, 1060, 1150, 1352, 1359, 1480, 1531, 1593*, 1621, 1636, 1683, 1758, 1831, 1859, 1944, 1960, 2059, 2477, 2549 (S/N =>10)	Not detected		m/z 1150, 1359, 1944, 3357 (S/N =>10)	Not detected
																	HPLC-UV	KTH						
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH				Yes	Clear bands below 10 kDa	No

INCT-1LS-100EL-R11M	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT	3,69	4,89		19.02.2024					MALDI-TOF	KTH	No peaks with S/N=>10	Not detected		m/z 494, 502, 504, 543, 575, 657, 799, 886, 913, 928, 944, 971 (S/N=>10)	Not detected
																	HPLC-UV	KTH					
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Blue smear below 10 kDa	No
INCT-5LS-1EL-R11M	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT	3,31	3,37		19.02.2024					MALDI-TOF	KTH					
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH		Unclear		No	No
INCT-5LS-5EL-R11M	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	5 kGy	RT	3,31	3,76		19.02.2024					MALDI-TOF	KTH					
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Band around 10 kDa	No
INCT-5LS-10EL-R11M	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT	3,31	3,87		19.02.2024					MALDI-TOF	KTH					
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Bands below 10 kDa	No
INCT-5LS-20EL-R11M	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	20 kGy	RT	3,31	3,98		19.02.2024					MALDI-TOF	KTH					
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Bands below 10 kDa	No
INCT-5LS-50EL-R11M	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT	3,31	3,25		19.02.2024					MALDI-TOF	KTH					
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Blue smear below 10 kDa	No
INCT-5LS-100EL-R11M	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT	3,31	4,94		19.02.2024					MALDI-TOF	KTH					
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Blue smear below 10 kDa	No
INCT-1LS-1EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT	3,69	3,27		19.02.2024			lyophilized		SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Clear bands below 10 kDa	No
INCT-1LS-5EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	5 kGy	RT	3,69	3,26		19.02.2024			lyophilized								
INCT-1LS-10EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT	3,69	3,54		19.02.2024			lyophilized		SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Clear bands below 10 kDa	No
INCT-1LS-20EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	20 kGy	RT	3,69	3,95		19.02.2024			lyophilized								
INCT-1LS-50EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT	3,69	3,97		19.02.2024			lyophilized		SDS-PAGE	KTH		Yes		Blue smear below 10 kDa	No

INCT-1LS-100EL-R11M-lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT	3,69	4,89		19.02.2024			lyophilized		SDS-PAGE	KTH				Yes	Blue smear below 10 kDa	No	
INCT-5LS-1EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT	3,31	3,37		19.02.2024			lyophilized		SDS-PAGE	KTH				Unclear	No	No	
INCT-5LS-5EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	5 kGy	RT	3,31	3,76		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-5LS-10EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT	3,31	3,87		19.02.2024			lyophilized		SDS-PAGE	KTH				Yes	Bands below 10 kDa	No	
INCT-5LS-20EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	20 kGy	RT	3,31	3,98		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-5LS-50EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT	3,31	3,25		19.02.2024			lyophilized		SDS-PAGE	KTH				Yes	Blue smear below 10 kDa	No	
INCT-5LS-100EL-R11M_lio	INCT	KTH	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT	3,31	4,94		19.02.2024			lyophilized		SDS-PAGE	KTH				Yes	Blue smear below 10 kDa	No	
INCT-1LS-1EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT	3,69	3,27		19.02.2024													
INCT-1LS-5EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	5 kGy	RT	3,69	3,26		19.02.2024													
INCT-1LS-10EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT	3,69	3,54		19.02.2024													
INCT-1LS-20EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	20 kGy	RT	3,69	3,95		19.02.2024													
INCT-1LS-50EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT	3,69	3,97		19.02.2024													
INCT-1LS-100EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT	3,69	4,89		19.02.2024													
INCT-5LS-1EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT	3,31	3,37		19.02.2024													
INCT-5LS-5EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	5 kGy	RT	3,31	3,76		19.02.2024													
INCT-5LS-10EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT	3,31	3,87		19.02.2024													
INCT-5LS-20EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	20 kGy	RT	3,31	3,98		19.02.2024													
INCT-5LS-50EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT	3,31	3,25		19.02.2024													
INCT-5LS-100EL-R11M	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT	3,31	4,94		19.02.2024													
INCT-1LS-1EL-R11M_lio	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT	3,69	3,27		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-1LS-5EL-R11M_lio	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	5 kGy	RT	3,69	3,26		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-1LS-10EL-R11M_lio	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT	3,69	3,54		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-1LS-20EL-R11M_lio	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	20 kGy	RT	3,69	3,95		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-1LS-50EL-R11M_lio	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT	3,69	3,97		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-1LS-100EL-R11M-lio	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT	3,69	4,89		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-5LS-1EL-R11M_lio	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT	3,31	3,37		19.02.2024			lyophilized										
INCT-5LS-5EL-R11M_lio	INCT	IST-ID	N2	1 M 2-propanol	5 mg/ml	EB/EL	5 kGy	RT	3,31	3,76		19.02.2024			lyophilized										

Sample: Ovotransferrin

IRRADIATION									pH			DATE			STORAGE	ANALYSIS									
Sample ID	Institute	Place of delivery	Atmosphere	Solution composition	Concentration	Source	Dose	Temperature	Before irradiation	After irradiation	After shipment/ before analysis	Analysis													
												of irradiation	of receipt	of analysis	Type of storage	Visual observations	Analysis method	Analysis performed at	Consumption of native protein	Fragments	Aggregates	Consumption of native protein	Fragments	Aggregates	
INCT-1GOTD-11L-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	1 kGy	RT				24.10.2022				RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	No	No		Yes		
INCT-1GOTD-10L-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	10 kGy	RT				24.10.2022				RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	No	No		Yes	Yes	
INCT-1GOTD-5L-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	5 kGy	RT				24.10.2022													
INCT-1GOTD-10L-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	10 kGy	RT				24.10.2022													
INCT-1GOTD-25L-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	25 kGy	RT				24.10.2022													
INCT-10TS-1EL-RN/ INCT-10TS-1EL-RNPO	INCT	KTH	N2O	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-1EL-RA/ INCT-10TS-1EL-RAPO	INCT	KTH	Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-1EL-RI/ INCT-10TS-1EL-RIPO	INCT	KTH	N2	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-1EL-RNP/ INCT-10TS-1EL-RNPOP	INCT	KTH	N2O	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				31.01.2023				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-1EL-RAP/ INCT-10TS-1EL-RAPOP	INCT	KTH	Air	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-1EL-RIP/ INCT-10TS-1EL-RIPOP	INCT	KTH	N2	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				06.12.2022				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-10EL-RN/ INCT-10TS-10EL-RNPO	INCT	KTH	N2O	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-10EL-RA/ INCT-10TS-10EL-RAPO	INCT	KTH	Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-10EL-RI/ INCT-10TS-10EL-RIPO	INCT	KTH	N2	H2O	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few
INCT-10TS-10EL-RNP/ INCT-10TS-10EL-RNPOP	INCT	KTH	N2O	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				31.01.2023				Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No				Few

INCT-10TS-10EL-RAP/ INCT-10TS-10EL-RAPOP	INCT	KTH	Air	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No			Few	
INCT-10TS-10EL-RAP/ INCT-10TS-10EL-RAPOP	INCT	KTH	N2	Phosphate buffer	1 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				06.12.2022			Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No			Few	
INCT-20TS-1EL-RN/ INCT-20TS-1EL-RNPO	INCT	EPS	N2O	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RA/ INCT-20TS-1EL-RAPO	INCT	EPS	Air	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RI/ INCT-20TS-1EL-RIPO	INCT	EPS	N2	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RNP/ INCT-20TS-1EL-RNPOP	INCT	EPS	N2O	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RAP/ INCT-20TS-1EL-RAPOP	INCT	EPS	Air	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RIP/ INCT-20TS-1EL-RIPOP	INCT	EPS	N2	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-10EL-RN/ INCT-20TS-10EL-RNPO	INCT	EPS	N2O	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-10EL-RA/ INCT-20TS-10EL-RAPO	INCT	EPS	Air	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-10EL-RI/ INCT-20TS-10EL-RIPO	INCT	EPS	N2	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-10EL-RNP/ INCT-20TS-10EL-RNPOP	INCT	EPS	N2O	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-10EL-RAP/ INCT-20TS-10EL-RAPOP	INCT	EPS	Air	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-10EL-RAP/ INCT-20TS-10EL-RAPOP	INCT	EPS	N2	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	10 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RN	INCT	IST-ID	N2O	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RI	INCT	IST-ID	N2	H2O	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RNP	INCT	IST-ID	N2O	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												
INCT-20TS-1EL-RAP	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Phosphate buffer	2 mg/ml	EB/EL	1 kGy	RT				14.02.2023												

INCT-0.1GOTD-200EL-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT			23.03.2023			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No specific peaks with S/N => 10 could be detected.	No	Yes	578 (S/N => 10)	No	
																HPLC-UV	KTH	Yes	No	No				
INCT-0.1GOTD-300EL-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT			23.03.2023			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No specific peaks with S/N => 10 could be detected.	No	Yes	578 (S/N => 10)	No	
																HPLC-UV	KTH	Yes	No	No				
																SDS-PAGE	KTH	Yes	Blue smear below 80 kDa	No	Yes	Blue smear below 80 kDa	No	
INCT-OTD-400EL-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	400 kGy	RT			11.10.2023			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No specific peaks with S/N => 10 could be detected.	No	Yes	578 (S/N => 10)	No	
																HPLC-UV	KTH	Yes	No	No				
																SDS-PAGE	KTH	Yes	Blue smear below 80 kDa	No	Yes	Blue smear below 80 kDa	No	
INCT-OTD-500EL-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	500 kGy	RT			11.10.2023			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	No specific peaks with S/N => 10 could be detected.	No	Yes	578 (S/N => 10)	No	
																HPLC-UV	KTH	Yes	No	No				
																SDS-PAGE	KTH	Yes	Blue smear below 80 kDa	No	Yes	Blue smear below 80 kDa	No	
INCT-0.1GOTD-50EL-RI	INCT	KTH	N2	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT			23.03.2023			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes						
INCT-0.1GOTD-100EL-RI	INCT	KTH	N2	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT			23.03.2023			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes				Yes		
INCT-0.1GOTD-200EL-RI	INCT	KTH	N2	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT			23.03.2023			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes						
INCT-0.1GOTD-300EL-RI	INCT	KTH	N2	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT			23.03.2023			RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes						
INCT-0.1GOTD-50EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT			23.03.2023													
INCT-0.1GOTD-100EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT			23.03.2023													

	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	γ-source	0.36 kGy	RT						Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Yes				
	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	γ-source	1.1 kGy	RT						Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Yes		-	Yes	
	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	γ-source	2.2 kGy	RT						Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Yes				
	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	γ-source	3.6 kGy	RT						Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Yes				
	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	γ-source	11 kGy	RT						Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes	Yes				
	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	10 mg/ml	γ-source	3.6 kGy	RT						Freezer, -18° C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
INCT-OTD-25EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	25 kGy	RT				11.10.2023											
INCT-OTD-100EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT				11.10.2023											
INCT-OTD-400EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	400 kGy	RT				11.10.2023											
INCT-OTD-500EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	500 kGy	RT				11.10.2023											

Sample: **Ovalbumin**

IRRADIATION										pH		DATE		STORAGE	ANALYSIS									
Sample ID	Institute	Place of delivery	Atmosphere	Solution composition	Concentration	Source	Dose	Temperature	Before irradiation	After irradiation	After shipment / before analysis	Analysis												
												of irradiation	of receipt	of analysis	Type of storage	Visual observations	Analysis method	Analysis performed at	Consumption of native protein	Fragments	Aggregates	Consumption of native protein	Fragments	Aggregates
INCT-1GOD-5IL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	5 kGy	RT				24.10.2022												
INCT-1GOD-10IL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	10 kGy	RT				24.10.2022												
INCT-1GOD-25IL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/ILU	25 kGy	RT				24.10.2022												
INCT-OL-50EL-RA	INCT	EPS	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-OL-100EL-RA	INCT	EPS	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-OL-200EL-RA	INCT	EPS	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-OL-300EL-RA	INCT	EPS	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-OL-50EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT			6,3	17.05.2023	01-06-23	08-06-23	RT		Solubility test; DLS	UNIPA	No	No	Yes			
INCT-OL-100EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT			6,66	17.05.2023	01-06-23	08-06-23	RT		Solubility test; DLS	UNIPA	No	No	Yes			
INCT-OL-200EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT			6,95	17.05.2023	01-06-23	08-06-23	RT		Solubility test; DLS	UNIPA	No	No	Yes			
INCT-OL-300EL-RA	INCT	UNIPA	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT			7,01	17.05.2023	01-06-23	08-06-23	RT		Solubility test; DLS	UNIPA	No	No	No			
INCT-OL-50EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-OL-100EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-OL-200EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	200 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
INCT-OL-300EL-RA	INCT	IST-ID	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT				17.05.2023												
	KTH		Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	γ-source	0.36 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		Air	H2O	10 mg/ml	γ-source	0.36 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		Air	Dry	n/a	γ-source	0.36 kGy	RT							RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	γ-source	1.1 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		Air	H2O	10 mg/ml	γ-source	1.1 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		Air	Dry	n/a	γ-source	1.1 kGy	RT							RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		Air	H2O	1 mg/ml	γ-source	20.2 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		Air	H2O	10 mg/ml	γ-source	20.2 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		Air	Dry	n/a	γ-source	20.2 kGy	RT							RT		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	γ-source	0.36 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	γ-source	1.1 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						
	KTH		N2	1 M 2-propanol	1 mg/ml	γ-source	2.2 kGy	RT							Freezer, -18°C		MALDI-TOF	KTH						

																	SDS-PAGE	KTH	Strong bands below 85 kDa and 50 kDa, corresponding OVT and OVA	Bands below 85 kDa and 50 kDa. Blue smear around 40 kDa.	Blue smear below 200 kDa	Strong bands below 85 kDa and 50 kDa, corresponding OVT and OVA	Blue smear above and below 40 kDa	Blue smear below 200 kDa
INCT-EW-50EL-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	50 kGy	RT				24.04.2024				RT								
																	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Peak around 45 kDa corresponding to OVA. Peak around 14 kDa corresponding to LYZ	m/z 793, 897, 1294, 1466, 1716, 1844, 1972, 3344 (S/N =>10) however, low intensity	Not detected			
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH				Strong bands below 85 kDa and 50 kDa, corresponding OVT and OVA	Blue smear above and below 40 kDa	Blue smear below 200 kDa
INCT-EW-100EL-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	100 kGy	RT				24.04.2024				RT								
																	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Peak around 45 kDa corresponding to OVA. Peak around 14 kDa corresponding to LYZ	m/z 793, 897, 1294, 1466, 1716, 1844, 1972, 3344 (S/N =>10) however, low intensity	Not detected			
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH	Yes	Blue smear below 85 kDa and around 40 kDa.	Blue smear below 200 kDa	Faint blue bands below 85 kDa and 50 kDa, corresponding OVT and OVA	Blue smear above and below 40 kDa	Faint blue smear below 200 kDa
INCT-EW-300EL-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	300 kGy	RT				24.04.2024				RT								
																	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Yes, peak around 45 kDa is not detected. Peak around 14 kDa corresponding to LYZ	m/z 585, 899, 1297, 1469, 1720 (S/N =>10) however, low intensity	Not detected			
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH				Yes	Blue smear above and below 40 kDa	No
INCT-EW-500EL-RA	INCT	KTH	Air	Dry	n/a	EB/EL	500 kGy	RT				24.04.2024				RT								
																	MALDI-TOF	KTH	Peak around 14 kDa corresponding to LYZ	m/z 1296, 1469, 1719 (S/N =>10) however, low intensity	Not detected			
																	SDS-PAGE	KTH				Yes	Blue smear above and below 40 kDa	No

